

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14434220>

INTEGRATING A PSYCHOLINGUISTIC APPROACH TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATION PRACTICE

M.Abduganiyeva

ASIFL. Student. Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages Faculty of English language and literature.

Sh. Turg'unova

ASIFL. Student. Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages Faculty of English language and literature.

E.mail: abduganiyevamushtariy23@gmail.com

Anotation. *Currently, the only way to get education for children with various disabilities who need inclusive education is not enough to provide the student with the necessary equipment and conditions for the educational process. For this, it is important to properly plan lessons, taking into account all the age and psychophysical characteristics of students. Anamal children usually covered more, therefore, as much as possible, the lesson should be given a psycholinguistic orientation. This makes it easier for students to communicate with their peers and express their opinions.*

Keywords. *Anomalous children, psycholinguistics, communication, lesson, student, psychophysiological, intellectual, quality education, equal rights, inclusive education, integration, pedagogue, motivational*

Psycholinguistics studies communication in relation to the human brain and psychological characteristics. Inclusive education provides equal opportunities for all students regardless of their abilities, needs and differences. Integrating these two approaches can help students gain a deeper understanding of how to learn to communicate and create a personalized learning environment for students.

Psycholinguistics develops a model of human speech activity and psychophysiological formation and examines them in a psychological experimental way.[1]

Through the use of psycholinguistics in educational activities, the development of speech, listening comprehension, reading, writing, memory and logical thinking in students receiving inclusive education, raising their level of knowledge and spirituality, forming mental work skills and intellectual, emotional and motivational characteristics of the student.

The goal of inclusive education is to create a barrier-free, customized educational environment for students with special educational needs by using special tools and methods at school, involving special pedagogues, by effectively adapting them to society and developing them in all aspects. consists of is to provide quality education that serves harmony.[2]

Considers how integrating psycholinguistic principles into inclusive education practices can influence language processing and acquisition, comprehension and teaching methods, assessment strategies, and diverse learner support systems, provides equal learning outcomes

The impact of language on academic achievement in psycholinguistic education and inclusive education:

Students learn to communicate through their cultural and social experiences.

Students are actively involved in language learning and receive, analyze, and learn new information. Each student learns to communicate at a certain speed and in a unique way. Psycholinguistic principles form a culturally customized education, taking into account the use of different language resources and the origin of students in language. Facilitates expression .. Data analysis avoids subjectivity in interpreting students 'skill level, taking into account knowledge and strengths. On the other hand, psycholinguistic principles define the design of evaluation, providing fairness and convenience to a variety of students. Psycholinguistic practices in inclusive education require a variety of cognitive directions and teaching methods tailored to the needs of

the child, which creates equal opportunities for everyone. In inclusive education, the system of integration of psycholinguistics requires the following goals and objectives:

- Creation of necessary psychological-pedagogical, correctional conditions for education of disabled children and adolescents, implementation of educational programs for spiritual development, social adjustment and implementation of correctional work aimed at their potential in an educational institution
- Guaranteeing students' right to equality in education;
- Satisfaction of children with active participation of society and family, early adaptation to social life;
- Giving disabled children and teenagers the right to live without family;
- The opportunity in society is to form a friendly and loving attitude towards children and teenagers. [3]

Inclusive education psycholinguistics studies the education, speech, emotional, voluntary and development of mental processes in children, the identification of mental characteristics, the development of various activities, learning, labor development, the formation of the child as a person through communication. A psycholinguistic approach and inclusive education together help to create a positive and supportive learning environment. Teachers try to help students feel comfortable and express their thoughts freely. This helps students feel in a safe and supportive environment and expresses their thoughts freely. A positive learning environment increases students' confidence.

Integrating a psycholinguistic approach into inclusive education encourages students to actively participate in their learning and provides many opportunities to develop their communication skills. Observing their progress and success in developing communication skills will increase students' self-confidence.

There can be a number of problems in the integration of psycholinguistics into inclusive education. These include:

Psycholinguistics requires a variety of teaching materials and methods to meet the needs of the learner. Inclusive education requires additional resources to meet the

diverse needs of students. A lack of resources, as well as financial constraints, lack of teacher training opportunities, and lack of teaching materials can make it difficult to fully integrate a psycholinguistic approach into inclusive education.

The psycholinguistic approach requires students to activate their knowledge. Some students, especially those with language learning difficulties, may not be interested in actively engaging themselves in learning. When integrating the psycholinguistic approach into inclusive education, it is important to increase students' enthusiasm and actively involve them in reading.

Conclusion: Despite these difficulties, the integration of the psycholinguistic approach into inclusive education is a promising approach to improve students' language learning efficiency. For this integration to be successful, attention must be paid to resource allocation, teacher training, consideration of student diversity, improved assessment methods, and student motivation.

References:

1. INKLUZIV TA'LIMDA PSIXOLINGVISTIKA Abdug'aniyeva Mushtariy Muzaffarjon qizi
2. Psychology <http://info-tashxis.uz/home/SinglePage/6465>
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/inklyuziv-ta-limda-nogiron-bollalarni-o-qitish-va-tarbiyalash-muammolari>
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378203213_Umumta'lim_maktablari_da_inklyuziv_ta'lim_jarayonining_ijtimoiy-psixologik_mexanizmlarini_takomillashtirish
5. <http://ocutus.ucr.edu>
6. <http://www.ziyo-net.uz>
7. <http://www.kutubxona.uz>